

An Efficient Protocol For Computations Delegation Using Rerandomizable Garbled Circuits

Abstract. We consider the problem of delegating computations, in which a client may outsource the computation of a function, represented as a boolean circuit, to an external entity, then receives the result and a proof of correctness that can be verified efficiently. Most existing non-interactive solutions rely on the use of fully homomorphic encryption [11], which is practically unaffordable. As it turns out, making a probabilistic assumption about the honesty of the external entity eliminates the need for FHE [3]. This paper describes an efficient protocol for delegating computations that also guarantees input and output privacy. The protocol is a new variant of the multi-server model and the cycle architecture from Ananth et al., which is based on the assumption of the existence of at least one honest server [3]. We carefully utilize an alternative re-randomizable variant of Yao’s garbled circuits based on the ElGamal encryption scheme [8], which leads to a secure, private, and efficient protocol based on the DDH assumption. Furthermore, we describe an example implementation of an application of the protocol: a fully decentralized verifiable system for outsourcing computations, VDCCS, which serves as a proof-of-concept prototype.

Keywords: Yao’s Garbled Circuits · Delegating Computations · Homomorphic Encryption · ElGamal Encryption · Secure Multi-party Computation · Non-interactive Protocols

1 INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

Sharing computational resources has become an important area of research since there is an ever-increasing demand for computational power, and it has become no longer practical to rely solely on vertical scaling while addressing this demand [34]. Therefore, an alternative way to solve this problem would be sharing resources over a network. To rephrase the problem statement, suppose that Alice wants to compute a function f but lacks the computational power needed to compute it. On the other hand, Bob, who has another machine, has this computational power that Alice needs. So, Alice would outsource the computation of the function to Bob, who would run it on his machine and return the results to Alice. Of course, many challenges immediately arise when considering such solutions.

The very first challenge we are faced with is verifiability. In order for the solution to be valid, it has to guarantee that Bob would actually return the correct results to Alice. This is because the outsourcing will happen essentially

on a network having possibly malicious Bobs out there, who could pretend to have computed the function and return the wrong results. The result returned must be *easily* verifiable by Alice; otherwise, she will never know whether it was the right answer because the only way then would be to naively re-compute the function on her end, which is not affordable by definition. Thus, a valid solution should guarantee that Bob will return nothing but the correct answer. Therefore, verifiability is a critical challenge that we will be trying to solve. To restate the problem accurately, Alice wants to outsource the computation of a function f on a network where Bob would compute it and return a verifiable result to Alice.

The second challenge we are faced with is the complexity of verifying the result as compared to doing the computation itself from scratch. From the above, it is clear that the cost of verification must not exceed the cost of redoing the computation and should not scale with the complexity of the computation.

The third main challenge is privacy. Indeed, the computation that Alice wants to outsource could be a sensitive computation on sensitive data, so the privacy of the computation as well as the data should be guaranteed. Thus, finally, what a valid solution would achieve is to guarantee that Bob would do the computation and return the correct results to Alice without jeopardizing the privacy of the data nor the computation.

In this work, we propose an efficient protocol, a variation of [3], with an alternative construction of re-randomizable garbled circuits based on ElGamal encryption [8] utilizing some of the techniques in [21] to compose a valid solution given the assumptions and setting at hand, which we state later. Afterward, we move from theory to practice in the later sections of the paper, where we outline our current implementation of a decentralized, verifiable computing resources sharing system based on the ideas introduced; this serves as a proof-of-concept prototype. Finally, we conclude with final remarks regarding this work and possible pathways for future work.

Before the protocol is introduced, we begin by summarizing the relevant background and related work that would help the reader grasp the content of this paper.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Secure Multi-Party Computation

Secure multi-party computation protocols are protocols carried out among a group of distrustful parties to securely compute a function f on a joint set of private inputs that each of the parties has. The protocol should achieve *secrecy* (keeping the inputs private) and *correctness* (guaranteeing that the function is computed correctly). Thus, the protocols should provably reveal nothing beyond the result of the function [12, 14, 32] and often rely on techniques such as secret sharing ([27] c.f. [4] for a survey).

Security of multi-party computation protocol is defined using *efficient simulators*. This simulation paradigm ensures that anything that a subset of colluding

participants can learn by participating in the protocol could have been learnt by interacting with an efficient simulator (c.f. [18] for details about simulation-based proofs).

2.2 Yao's 2-PC Garbled Circuit Protocol

Detailed Description In the original proposal of circuit garbling, Yao [32] introduced a protocol for secure 2-party computation which involved two players: a *garbler* and an *evaluator*. Yao considered as a motivating example the millionaire problem where there are two millionaires: Alice and Bob who want to know who is richer without sharing the exact amount of their wealth with each other. Therefore, for Alice's wealth a and Bob's wealth b , we want to compute the Boolean value of the inequality ($a < b$ ¹). Let's consider Alice will play the role of the garbler P_1 , while Bob will play the role of the evaluator P_2 . Now, P_1 and P_2 have to collaboratively follow a protocol involving secret exchanging in order to find the output of the proposed function.

First, the garbler represents the function f into a Boolean circuit C . Then, the garbler transforms C into C_g by garbling each gate's computation table of the circuit. Except for output wires, P_1 garbles every wire by replacing all Boolean values in the computation tables with pseudo-random strings while keeping the mapping table secret. This process creates a garbled circuit C_g . Since P_1 has private input a , she expresses it in terms of the labels of the garbled circuit matching her secret mapping. The garbler then sends the garbled circuit C_g and her garbled input a_g [5, 14, 16, 29, 32, 33].

P_2 , the evaluator, receives the garbled circuit and the input wires of P_1 . Since P_2 does not know the secret mapping, he will not be able to know the value of the private input of P_1 . However, P_2 will not be able to represent his private input in the same pseudo-random representation without knowledge of the mapping. In order to achieve that, P_2 engages in a *1-out-of-2 oblivious transfer* red citation needed with P_1 for each bit of P_2 's input. Oblivious transfer enables the garbler to provide the evaluator with one of two possible encryptions (encryption of 0 or 1) without the garbler knowing which one it sent. We do not explain the details of oblivious transfer here, but refer the reader to [14, 17, 26, 29] for details.

Now, P_2 has access to the garbled circuit C_g , his private input, and P_1 's private input; both represented as pseudo-random strings according to the secret mapping generated by P_1 . Therefore, P_2 can carry out the computation by ungarbling the gates one by one using the given input wires. Only one entry of each table would be ungarbled as its inputs match the given inputs of P_1 and P_2 . Then, P_2 continues to ungarble the rest of the gates using the output wires of the previous gates. The process goes on until P_2 reaches the output gate. P_2 then concludes the protocol by sharing the results with P_1 . It is essential to note that P_2 will not be able to infer the private input of P_1 by observing the execution of the computations on the gates because the way the tables are constructed prevents that [5, 14, 16, 29, 32, 33]. Thus, Alice and Bob were able to

¹ For simplicity let's consider the case where $a \neq b$.

compute their desired function on their private inputs. Neither Alice nor Bob knew any information about the other’s private inputs except for what could be inferred from the result.

Circuit Garbling Let’s revisit the process of circuit garbling in more detail. As previously mentioned, input wires of the first gate(s) are mapped into pseudo-random strings. The output wires of each gate go as input wires to gates on the next level until the final gate(s). Only the final gate(s) have output wires that cannot be input wires to any other gate. Input wires of the first gates cannot be output wires. Following up on that, the construction of the computation table of each gate after garbling has transformed from being $\{0, 1\} \times \{0, 1\} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ into a more complex mapping that hides the information in the table. Therefore, it becomes a mapping from a set of pseudo-random strings to another set of uniformly distributed pseudo-random strings that are computed based on the input strings. Thus the truth table becomes a mapping of $f(\{0, 1\}^k \times \{0, 1\}^k) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^k$, where f is a *universal one-way hash function* and k is the fixed length of the hash function’s output [5, 14, 16, 29, 32, 33].

It is important to note that P_1 only sends the garbled values to P_2 . This includes only the final column of table 3. P_1 also garbles her input value by representing each bit as the corresponding pseudo-random string mapping. She does the same for the private input of P_2 utilizing 1-out-of-2 oblivious transfer. Further details on the proof of security for Yao’s Garbled Circuit protocol could be found in [20].

Table 1: Truth table of the AND gate and its garbled truth table.

W_a	W_b	W_c
0	0	0
0	1	0
1	0	0
1	1	1

W_a	W_b	W_c	Garbled Values
k_a^0	k_b^0	k_c^0	$H(k_a^0 k_b^0 g_{id}^{AND}) \oplus k_c^0$
k_a^0	k_b^1	k_c^0	$H(k_a^0 k_b^1 g_{id}^{AND}) \oplus k_c^0$
k_a^1	k_b^0	k_c^0	$H(k_a^1 k_b^0 g_{id}^{AND}) \oplus k_c^0$
k_a^1	k_b^1	k_c^1	$H(k_a^1 k_b^1 g_{id}^{AND}) \oplus k_c^1$

(a) Truth table of AND gate

(b) Garbled truth table of AND gate, where H is a hashing function that behaves like a random oracle

Challenges and Optimizations Some challenges face the original protocol. The first one is how to guarantee that P_1 conducts the garbling correctly. This could be resolved by using the techniques of *cut-and-choose* protocol [19] (c.f. [1, 31, 19] for details). Another technique to solve this problem, as well as the case of P_2 being malicious, is role exchanging between the garbler and evaluator

every round. Before protocol termination, players check if the output value of the first round matches the output value of the second round. If this is true, then the protocol was executed successfully. Otherwise, the execution fails, and the protocol terminates as at least one of the two players was proven to be malicious [14, 15].

Ever since the original publication of Yao’s protocol [32, 33], there have been many optimizations of garbled circuit construction such as *free-XOR* [16], *garbled row reduction* [22, 24], *half-gates* [35], and *fixed-key AES garbling* [5]. In brief, applying the proposed optimizations reduce the number of pseudo-random strings, the ciphertexts, that are present in each non-XOR gate’s computation table to only two ciphertexts, while performing the garbling on XOR gates without the need of ciphertext or any encryption operations, and so it is computed for free.

Garbled circuits now became an essential cryptographic building block, and effort was made to optimize the process and efficiently implement it independently of any underlying protocol. One of the examples of such protocol-independent garbled circuit construction and evaluation systems is the *JustGarble* System [5]. JustGarble is a system for garbling and evaluating Boolean circuits. It could be used for building Boolean circuits and garbling them with the optimizations stated as well as evaluating the circuit. The challenge of generating Boolean circuits from functions remains a huge limitation for circuit-based multi-party computation protocol. We will postpone the discussion of this challenge until we explain our system construction in which we resolve this problem.

2.3 Outsourcing Computation Using Garbled Circuits

In this section, we discuss circuit-based protocols that were developed to achieve verifiable computing. Therefore, before discussing the protocols, let’s define *Verifiable Computing* as the ability of a potentially computationally weak client to outsource the computation of a function f on an input vector $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ to a server or a group of servers maintaining that after the outsourcing protocol is completed, the client should receive the result of the computation along with a proof of its correctness [3, 9].

Utilizing Fully Homomorphic Encryption Outsourcing computation using Yao’s Garbled Circuit protocol was first tackled in [9]. The proposed protocol is a 2-party protocol: a client and a server. Relating to the protocol mentioned in section ??, the client will play the role of garbler while the server will play the role of the evaluator. However, in the protocol discussed in [9], only the client has private input and knowledge of the underlying function. Therefore, they proposed to use both Yao’s Garbled circuits and *Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE)* [10] to achieve verifiability and input/output privacy for the client [9]. Although the protocol achieves verifiability, the amount of computations done by the client is significant in comparison to computing the underlying function on her own. It is worth noting that the garbled circuit should not be used more than once as it raises the possibility of a specific adversary to know more information about the underlying circuit [9]. An obvious but not practical solution

for this problem is that the client needs to re-generate the garbled circuit before outsourcing it again. However, this client is supposedly computationally weak, and the garbling process can be relatively close to computing the function [9].

The protocol in [9] used FHE to solve this problem and enable using the garbled circuit more than once [9]. FHE is useful in this matter as it provides the capability to perform operations on encrypted data while keeping both the input data and the output private. Hence, the server will not be able to view the actual data being operated on. Thus, it cannot get any information about the underlying function or garbled circuit [9]. However, the security of the protocol is based on the assumption that the number of malformed responses k sent by the worker should be sufficiently less than the security parameter λ . The client chooses the security parameter λ as the length of the ciphertext of the generated wires [9].

We now describe the protocol.

1. The client generates the public and private keys that she will maintain through the lifetime of the channel between the client and the worker.
2. Then, she chooses a ciphertext of length λ to represent each wire in the circuit, as explained earlier [9]. This stage, although computationally demanding, is done only once because of the use of FHE.
3. The next step is preparing the keys to encrypt each output-wire in the circuit. This is done by running a doubly homomorphic encryption scheme to generate new key pairs from the already generated ones [9].
4. The client constructs the garbled circuit by encrypting the wires using the newly generated keys. Then, sending the garbled circuit along with the client's input represented in the proper format of ciphertexts to the worker in order to evaluate it [9].
5. The fourth and final step is the output computation and verification stage. In this stage, the worker evaluates the garbled circuit using the provided input. He then sends the encrypted output to the client.
6. The client proceeds to decrypt the output and to check its validity. The final stage takes relatively as much time as the mentioned preprocessing stage [9].

The protocol achieved three essential goals [9]: firstly, releasing the client from the burden of re-creating the garbled circuit at each computation. Secondly, it achieved verifiability using Yao's garbled circuit construction. Finally, it achieved input and output privacy [9]. However, it does not achieve privacy for the function f . Nonetheless, it is worth mentioning that function privacy can be guaranteed by using universal circuits $UC(c, x)$ that can evaluate a circuit c , described as a bit string and given as an *input* to UC over an input x . In that case, due to input privacy, function privacy follows [2]. However, as Anath et al. [3] notes in a similar context, this is mostly useful only when f is easy to describe but is of high computational complexity.

Removing FHE and Preprocessing The second protocol of interest expands on the protocol discussed in the previous section by pointing out its problems

as we mentioned and proposing a solution to overcome them [3]. They improved the previous protocol to remove the FHE from the entire process, as well as to free the client from the preprocessing stage which is almost as expensive as computing the underlying function by moving the processing to the online stage [3]. It utilizes one-way functions and trapdoor functions to solve this problem. However, it requires at least two workers computing the function of a single client, and the protocol assumes that at least there is one honest, non-colluding worker.

The protocol is based on Re-randomizable Garbled Circuits [11]. Garbled circuits could be re-randomized by generating a new garbled circuit GC_2 from an existing garbled circuit GC_1 , where GC_2 is the same as GC_1 and is indistinguishable from it. Re-randomization is achieved by making the encryption process of the wires follow a multiplicative homomorphic encryption scheme [3, 11]. Re-randomization also goes for garbling the input and output wires, as the client could garble or re-randomize them independent of internal wires and independent of the circuit. For example, if Bob re-randomized the internal wires of GC_1 to be GC_2 , Alice could use the same seed to re-randomize the input wires (in_1) and get (in_2) which only can be used by GC_2 . The protocol considers the removal of preprocessing and FHE in two scenarios. The first is the 2-worker case, which we will not discuss in this paper. The second scenario is the n-case scenario. In this model, there are more than two workers, namely n workers. The model also utilizes a re-randomization scheme, as the garbled circuit and input wires will be re-randomized for security and removing FHE from the protocol [3]. The model is explained as follows: the first worker will get the Boolean circuit from the client and generate GC_1 with its input and output wires. The workers from 2 till $n-1$ will re-randomize the input wires and GC_1 generating $GC_2, GC_3, \dots, GC_{n-1}$. The final worker, worker n, should evaluate GC_{n-1} using the input ciphertexts that will be sent from the client directly [3]. After evaluation, the worker sends the result back to the client. Then, the client checks the validity of the results. Therefore, the client re-randomizes the input-wires and output-wires $n-1$ times, this should give him the same input-wires and output-wires resulting from re-randomizing the original circuit $n-1$ times [3]. Thus, the client could tell which worker cheated based on the validity of input wires that will be sent back to him at the end of the protocol. Secondly, the client would validate the result sent from the final worker against the valid output wires that he generated to make sure it is indeed a correct result for GC_{n-1} . The protocol also assumes the existence of at least one honest, non-colluding worker. Therefore, the security of the protocol now depends on two parameters n : the number of participating servers, and λ the length of the ciphertext representing each wire [3].

Now we can now describe the protocol [3] as follows:

1. All parties exchange public keys.
2. The Client:
 - (a) The client first generates the correlated randomness to be used by the $n-1$ servers. He generates a pseudo-random seed for each server to

garble the input wires, the output wires, and the rest of the circuit. This implies that each server would receive three seeds: R_{in} , R_{out} , and R_{GC} .

- (b) The client gives the computation a random id.
 - (c) The client uses the seed R_{in} of the first server S_1 along with id to generate the input-wires of GC_1 and then uses the seeds of the other servers S_2, \dots, S_{n-1} to re-randomize the input-wires.
 - (d) He then converts his private input into ciphertext of valid input-wires after re-randomization $n - 1$ times. He does the same for the output wires.
 - (e) The client then commits each group of seeds to the public key of each server, respectively, utilizing Non-Interactive Zero Knowledge Proof, NIZK, methodology.
 - (f) Each commitment is put in a message decrypted asymmetrically using the public key of the corresponding server S_i .
 - (g) Only the message sent to S_1 includes the circuit that the client wishes to compute, and only the message sent to S_n includes the ciphertext representing the client's private input.
 - (h) The client then proceeds to send the array of encrypted messages to S_1 after signing each message with his private key.
3. Server S_1 :
 - (a) Decrypts his own message.
 - (b) Verifies the signature of the client.
 - (c) Garbles the circuit provided with the given randomization seeds: R_{in} , R_{out} , and R_{GC} and the computation id.
 - (d) Computes a proof for the NIZK protocol.
 - (e) Creates a message with GC_1 and the NIZK proof for S_2 and the client, encrypted with their public keys, respectively.
 - (f) Finally, forwards the array of messages to S_2 with his new messages appended.
 4. Servers S_2, S_3, \dots, S_{n-1} :
 - (a) Decrypts his own message from the client and S_{i-1} .
 - (b) Verifies the signature of the client and S_{i-1} .
 - (c) Re-randomizes the garbled circuit provided with the given randomization seeds: R_{in} , R_{out} , and R_{GC} and the computation id.
 - (d) Computes a proof for the NIZK protocol.
 - (e) Creates a message with GC_i and the NIZK proof for S_{i+1} and the client, encrypted with their public keys, respectively.
 - (f) Finally, forwards the array of messages to S_{i+1} with his new messages appended.
 5. Server S_n :
 - (a) Decrypts his own message from the client and S_{n-1} .
 - (b) Verifies the signature of the client and S_{n-1} .
 - (c) Uses the input wires provided by the user to evaluate GC_{n-1} .
 - (d) Computes a proof for the NIZK protocol.
 - (e) Creates a message with GC_i and the NIZK proof for the client, encrypted with his public key.

- (f) Finally, forwards the array of messages to the client with his new messages appended.
- 6. The Client:
 - (a) Receives back the array of messages.
 - (b) Verify signatures.
 - (c) Validate the correctness of the final output and input wires. If they are malformed, then he proceeds to check the wires against each GC_i to find the cheating server S_i .
 - (d) Decodes the output received from S_n .

3 CONSIDERED MODEL AND ASSUMPTIONS

Back to our problem where a client C wishes to outsource the computation of $f(x)$, where f is a polynomial-time function representable by a Boolean circuit, to a serving entity S , which is potentially dishonest. Therefore, we attempt to solve this problem while guaranteeing *correctness*, that is, as we define, that the result returned to the client is correct with a high probability. Clearly, it is also attractive to achieve *privacy* of the input x , the function f , and the returned result $f(x)$. However, we exclude the privacy of the function f , as explained in the previous section, from the above list as a trade-off for efficiency (e.g., avoiding the cost of constructing and programming universal circuits). Optimizations like [13] can be applied to satisfy function privacy with much less impact on efficiency. We provide an application of the constructed protocol, Verifiable Decentralized Computing Resources Sharing System (VDCS) [23], which relies on an extensible shared repository of known circuits, which makes the need for function privacy, in that specific application, unnecessary.

The problem described so far has been, to the best of our knowledge, unsolvable without the use of a fully homomorphic encryption scheme in some way. Ananth et al. [3] considers a model where the entity S mentioned above is a set of multiple (> 1) servers, at least one of which is assumed to be honest.

4 SOLUTION OVERVIEW

Under this honest server assumption, it turns out possible to construct a non-interactive solution that does not rely on FHE by using the re-randomizable garbled circuits construction described by Gentry et al. [11] in a cycle configuration described by Anath et al. [3]. This solution relies mainly on the DDH assumption and uses the BHHO cryptosystem [6], created by Boneh D., Halevi S., Hamburg M., Ostrovsky R.; additionally, it requires other cryptographic primitives such as a separate proxy re-encryption scheme. We show that a more efficient solution is obtained by using a variant of re-randomizable garbled circuits based on the ElGamal [8] encryption scheme. In a different context about reverse firewalls, Mironov et al. [21] constructs an elegant variant of Yao's garbled circuits based on the ElGamal scheme, from which we adapt several techniques in our construction. The combination of these two methodologies, under the honest server

assumption, lets us simplify each of them and optimize out several intermediate procedures without compromising correctness or privacy.

5 RE-RANDOMIZABLE GARBLED CIRCUITS

Our construction flattens the ciphertexts of a typical Yao’s garbled circuits to become a single layer of encryption under the product of the input labels (which still lies in the label space); this is instead of having two layers of enveloped encryptions each under one of the input labels $\text{ENC}_a(\text{ENC}_b(z))$ [9, 19] or a single encryption under the hash of the concatenated labels $\text{ENC}_{h(a|b)}(z)$ [29]. We do that to be able to manipulate the ciphertext using the homomorphic properties of the ElGamal cryptosystem. The private keys are from the multiplicative group of integers modulo p . The messages encrypted, as usual with garbled circuits, are the wire labels, which also serve as private keys for proceeding in circuit evaluation. Note that the original construct relies on a symmetric encryption scheme, but this, of course, is not an issue here because we only care about decryption using the input labels.

We deal with the issue of the message space (labels from \mathbb{Z}_p^*) being the same as the private key space (also labels from \mathbb{Z}_p^*) by resorting to a commonly known solution. The prime number p must be chosen to be a safe prime, that is the case when $\frac{p-1}{2}$ is also prime. In this case, algorithms, such as the Pohlig-Hellman algorithm [25], cannot efficiently solve the discrete logarithm problem under \mathbb{Z}_p^* . To also provide security against probabilistic techniques (e.g., the Index calculus algorithm), p needs to be at least 1024 bits in length, which is enough by itself to make DLP intractable in \mathbb{Z}_p^* [28, 30]. An alternative solution would be to go back and limit our private key space to the group of quadratic residues, this makes the detection of DDH tuples hard in \mathbb{Z}_p^* and counters other probabilistic techniques based on calculating the Legendre symbol [30].

In order to support re-randomization, a couple of encryption schemes that allow for re-randomization have been studied in order to decide which one would suit our purposes. The first scheme [11] was based on encrypting a mask and then encrypting the xor of that mask with the ciphertext. It was based on the BHHO encryption scheme [6]. Therefore, for any label Z , the encryption will be the pair $(\text{ENC}(\delta), \text{ENC}(\delta \oplus Z))$. The second encryption scheme we looked at was based on encrypting the ciphertext under the ElGamal encryption scheme [21]. Thus, the encryption of Z was just simply the pairs (C_1, C_2) resulting from encrypting Z under ElGamal.

We tried to combine both of these schemes together in one scheme where we would use a mask δ and XOR it with the label Z but under the ElGamal encryption instead of BHHO. This is because we believed that ElGamal is easier to understand and deploy in code in comparison to BHHO without compromising the security of our encryption. However, this combination did not work because we discovered that decryption will not be possible under this scheme. That is why we decided to stick to the second scheme where we would just use the ElGamal encryption scheme to encrypt any given label Z .

We argue later in this paper that our system will be secure provided that certain parameters for ElGamal encryption are satisfied. Since the security of ElGamal stems from the discrete log problem which has no known efficient solution so far [8], then we need to make sure that our prime group is large enough such that it becomes harder to crack the encryption. Therefore, we suggest a bit length for the prime number P that is between 1024-2048 bits. Furthermore, for the private key x , we use a multiplication of two input labels, that are generated randomly, to generate it. The input labels could be large in length as well, which is another security parameter. Furthermore, we use random seeds in order to generate the labels that will be used to create and encrypt the garbled circuit.

To sum up, for garbling, we generate the input and output labels using three random seeds; one for the inputs, one for the outputs and one for everything in between. Then, for each gate, we use the multiplication of two input labels to encrypt the corresponding output label under ElGamal, where we have a large prime P in the public key. So, after the garbling, there will be a set of (C_1, C_2) pairs resulting from encryption for each single row in the original truth table of each gate.

After the first server garbles the circuit, it gets sent to the following server for re-randomization. This is achieved through a series of calculations that would result in having new ciphertexts that are encrypted under a new private key without knowing the original private key. This is based on modular roots. For each garbled value (C_1, C_2) , we know that they are on the form $(g^k, y^k Z)$ since they are encrypted under ElGamal, where (P, g, y) are the public key of encryption, k is a random number and y is $g \times x$ where x is the private key of encryption. Assuming that we would like to change the ciphertexts such that they can only be decrypted by a new private key which equals $x \times R$, then we should do the following building up upon the brief explanation in [21]:

1. Raise y to the power of R such that the public key becomes (P, g, y^R)
2. Compute the modular R th root of C_1 and multiply C_2 by R such that the garbled value becomes $(g^{k/R}, y^k \times Z \times R)$.
3. Encrypt the value 1 under the new Public key so we get the pair (g^r, y^{Rr}) where r is a random number.
4. Multiply the pairs resulting from 2. and 3. so the garbled value becomes $(g^{kr/R}, y^{k+Rr} \times Z \times R)$

This works because now the actual value of the output label has changed to $Z \times R$ and the value of the private key x has changed to $x \times R$. So, if we decrypt using the decryption formula of ElGamal, $C_2 / C_1^{\text{privatekey}}$, we will get $Z \times R$ which is the new expected ciphertext.

While the previous scheme works in theory, it is a bit harder to achieve in practice due to the hard nature of the modular root problem [7]. However, there is an easy way to get around this by choosing the values of R , for which there is an inverse in the group \mathbb{Z}_P^* . This is based on the theorem that states that if the greatest common divisor of R and $P - 1$ is 1, that is they are relatively prime, then the modular R th root of any element $c \in \mathbb{Z}_P^*$ exists and is easy to find.

Therefore, when R is chosen randomly, it is guaranteed that $\gcd(R, P - 1)$ is 1 in order to make the re-randomization scheme practical without compromising the security. This is due to the fact that the number of R 's that exist in \mathbb{Z}_p^* such that $\gcd(R, P - 1) = 1$ is large according to Euler's Totient function which states that the number of integers that are relatively prime to a prime number P is $P - 1$. While $P - 1$ is not a prime number, the fact that P itself is a large number ensures that even if the number of integers that are relatively prime to $P - 1$ is way less than $P - 1$, it will still be a large number. Therefore, this practical solution does not compromise security.

After passing through all the re-randomizing servers, the garbled circuit reaches the server that would evaluate it. The evaluator uses the input labels to decrypt the way through the circuit. In order for the evaluator to know whether decryption was successful, an encrypted hash of each final label is paired with each gate. If and only if the hash of the result of the decryption matches the included hash, the evaluator can detect a successful decryption and can then proceed through the circuit.

6 OUR PROPOSED CONSTRUCTION

For the sake of this explanation, assume we have one client node C and n server nodes: S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n . Yet, it is simple to see how this could be generalized to a system with multiple clients and multiple servers, and where single nodes could act as either clients or servers based on the type of operation. In this section we segment the operation of the system into three parts:

1. Cycle Execution.
2. Preprocessing.
3. Registration and Cycle Construction.

Although Cycle Execution comes last in the list of operations. For the sake of simplicity and to appreciate the advantages of parts ii and iii, we begin by explaining it.

6.1 Cycle Execution

We use for this section the construction explained earlier proposed by Ananth et al. [3]. However, our construction dictated some modifications to the original model. In our proposed construction, the final message in the message array sent from the client will only contain communication information and signature verification. Refer back to the background section for more details about the original construction or refer to the original paper [3]. Thus, the input wires delegated by the client to compute the circuit evaluation result will not be sent along with the array of messages. Instead, they will be sent separately in a direct message from the client to the evaluating server S_n whenever they are ready to be sent. This implies that now the cycle from C to S_n can be done in parallel

for multiple circuits since the client will not be waiting to receive the result of the execution until he sends the separate message to the evaluating server S_n .

In Fig. 1, we see that the only change from the original model is the final message that used to contain the re-randomized input wires In_{n-1} . This message is now handled differently, as explained.

Moreover, to allow for fault tolerance support in our system, we propose the following modification on the encryption scheme: Instead of encrypting the messages with the corresponding public keys of each server, we will instead use randomly generated symmetric keys. Those symmetric keys are to be sent along with each message. However, the symmetric key of each message will be encrypted using the public key of the corresponding server. Therefore, the encryption process on the client-side will go as follows for each message:

Fig. 1: New Cycle Model

1. Generate a symmetric key k_i for each message.
2. Encrypt each message msg_i with the corresponding k_i .
3. Encrypt each k_i with the corresponding PK_i .

Therefore, this will allow easily replacing any server node if it went down during the execution of the protocol by simply re-encrypting the symmetric key k_i with the new server's public key, instead of re-encrypting the whole message. Thus, the cycle could be dynamically changed, as re-encrypting a key is much cheaper, which allows for supporting fault-tolerance. However, the engineering of the fault-tolerance scheme itself will be left open for future works. All garbling operations should be optimized, as explained in the background section. We

suggest that re-randomization be implemented in the fashion we proposed in earlier sections. The security assumption remains the same from the original model, which is that we are assuming the existence of at least one honest server.

6.2 Preprocessing

The model explained so far can be used as a library or embedded into any system that would provide it with the relevant information of each node without too many restrictions. However, in this subsection and the following, we propose a wrapper around this system that we believe would make it complete and adds to its security.

As explained in the previous subsection, the model now could be parallelized because the client will not enter the busy-waiting state of waiting for his evaluation result until he actually needs it and sends the separate message containing the re-randomized input wires. Therefore, we suggest that instead of representing the entire client code in one big circuit representation, this will imply that S1 will have full knowledge about the client code, which compromises privacy. We propose that the code be segmented into smaller circuits then the client has the job of connecting each circuit's output to the next in order to maintain the original logic of the code. Therefore, if the client is to choose the parts of the code that he wants to outsource, the execution of the code will be hybrid, allowing the client not to pay for parts of the code that he could execute himself and not to risk outsourcing especially sensitive blocks of code that he does not want to outsource. While at the same time, have the luxury of outsourcing all blocks of code that he does not want to execute himself.

Thus, we propose to mark these blocks of code with some directive and indicator, while having a preprocessor scan the code and modify it before it is compiled. The preprocessor would replace each outsourcing request with a thread that starts at the beginning of the code specifying the circuit and its security parameters along with replacing the outsourcing line of code itself with a call to the evaluation function that would send for the evaluation request of the circuit whenever the input wires are ready. As shown in Fig. 2, now all garbling requests will be made in parallel in simultaneous threads while the rest of the code, including the evaluation blocks, will be executed sequentially. This parallelization process will save a significant amount of runtime if compared with the original sequential execution without preprocessing. This is allowed because the client does not have to enter a busy-wait state at the start of each cycle execution process. Now, the threads will run in parallel with the code execution itself and with each other, making the total runtime of the code equal to the run time of the longest cycle execution added to the run time of the rest of the client code from the first evaluation request until the end of the code. This allows the system to avoid the liability of the naturally long execution time of the cycle. The preprocessor should be optimized and support loop unrolling to allow for the outsourcing of complex code.

```

func main(){
    var x int
    var y int
    .....//Some code
    a := x * y
    .....//Some code
    b := x+y
    .....//Some code
    c := a-b
}

Preprocess →

func main(){
    go comWithServersToGarble(mul_32_32, cID=0)
    go comWithServersToGarble(add_32_32, cID=1)
    go comWithServersToGarble(sub_32_32, cID=2)
    var x int
    var y int
    .....//Some code
    a := comWithServersToEval( cID=0, x, y)
    .....//Some code
    b := comWithServersToEval( cID=1, x, y)
    .....//Some code
    c := comWithServersToEval( cID=2, a, b)
}
    
```

Fig. 2: Sample Preprocessing Result

6.3 Registration and Cycle Construction

In this subsection, we propose the edge of decentralization and how to achieve more privacy and anonymity in the system. For this purpose, we suggest either building the system on top of a blockchain or integrating the system into a blockchain. The purpose of the blockchain is to act as a ledger where all transactions between the different nodes are recorded as well as manage and keep track of the payment for each successful execution. For simplicity, let us assume that we have a directory of service DS. To use the system proposed in this section, client and server nodes will have to register into this DS. The registration message should provide the DS with the following:

1. Public Key.
2. Communication information.
3. Server Capabilities (in case it's a server node) this includes the following:
 - (a) The maximum number of gates the server is willing to garble/re-randomize/evaluate in a single request.
 - (b) The minimum fee charged per gate.

Clients and servers can register to the DS under different identities using different public keys. The whole communication process can be done solely on the blockchain. However, there is the option of having the cycle execution be done off the blockchain. We leave the semantics and engineering of the DS (i.e., implementing it as a smart contract) and the communication method to the future implementers of our proposed system. Nonetheless, we specify that the registration process contains the items listed above. As for the cycle construction process, it should go as follows:

1. The client would request a cycle containing:
 - (a) The circuit information: the number of gates as well as the maximum fee paid per gate.

- (b) The number of servers in the cycle.
 - (c) His public key. This is advised to be a different key for each request to achieve anonymity and privacy.
2. DS would then perform an optimized scheduling process on all the online servers available in its database to choose the best combination of servers for the client to pay the minimal amount possible with the minimal combination of server resources. The optimized scheduling will not be discussed in this paper and will be left for future work.
 3. The DS then sends the cycle back to the client and waits for the confirmation or any fault tolerance handling request to distribute the fee paid by the clients to the different servers in the cycle.

Following this scheme of anonymity, the function will have added privacy. This happens because now S1 does not have full knowledge of the client code and only one operation of it. Henceforth, by changing the client identity for each operation, the whole code would remain private despite sharing bits of it. We leave the optimization of the communication process, optimized scheduling, as well as fault-tolerance support to future works, although our proposed scheme facilitates the integration of these.

Moreover, the DS should contain a repository of circuits for different functions. Since the code is now segmented into smaller operations, these smaller operations will be shared among system users. These operations could be simple operations such as integer addition, multiplication, or equality checks, or they could be complex operations such as matrix multiplication, string matching, or other sophisticated circuits. The client would refer to the chosen circuit from the repository in his request to the first server, and the server would fetch it from the repository, or the client could send his own circuit along with the message. All nodes could add unique circuits to the repository for everyone else to use. Therefore, the circuit construction will happen on-the-fly, which further reduces the runtime.

7 Our Implemented Prototype

We have implemented four different prototypes for the purpose of proving the functionality of our proposed system. In each iteration, we removed one of our assumptions and implemented a couple of extra functionalities. We started with the pure cycle execution in prototype 1. Then, we added a central primitive directory of service in prototype 2. In prototype 3, we implemented our modification on the cycle model, proposed in the previous section as well as a primitive preprocessor. In prototype 4, we applied our proposed re-randomization scheme, enhanced the preprocessor, and implemented a decentralized directory of service as a smart contract in the EOS blockchain.

As prototype 4 is the most comprehensive, we will limit the discussion to it in this section.

The purpose of the prototype is to act merely as a proof-of-concept of our proposed scheme and not as a fully functional optimal system. The reader of the

document can refer to [23] for the details of the implementation and documentation.

We will segment this section into five parts:

1. Circuit Representation & Repo.
2. VDCS Library.
3. Client Nodes.
4. Server Nodes.
5. Decentralized Directory of Service.

7.1 Circuit Representation & Repo

We begin by the circuit representation in our prototypes. For this, we used JSON format for circuit representation to allow for it to be more readable by clients and easier to create and add to the universal JSON circuits' repository. The representation of each circuit is shown in Fig. 3. Here, input gates are gates that are connected to external input wires and internal output wires. Middle gates are gates that are connected to internal input and output wires. Output gates are gates that are connected to internal input wires and external output wires. The output from output gates cannot be connected to the input of input gates.

```

"Input Gates":{
  "GateID":    UNIQUE TOPOLOGICAL ID FOR THE GATE
  "GateInputs": [LIST OF INPUT WIRES LABEL]
  "TruthTable": [EACH ENTRY CORRESPONDS TO INPUT COMBINATION]
},
"Middle Gates":{
  "GateID":    UNIQUE TOPOLOGICAL ID FOR THE GATE
  "GateInputs": [LIST OF INPUT GATES IDS]
  "TruthTable": [EACH ENTRY CORRESPONDS TO INPUT COMBINATION]
},
"Output Gates":{
  "GateID":    UNIQUE TOPOLOGICAL ID FOR THE GATE
  "GateInputs": [LIST OF INPUT GATES IDS]
  "TruthTable": [EACH ENTRY CORRESPONDS TO INPUT COMBINATION]
}

```

Fig. 3: Circuit Representation

The gate connections are represented in the GateInputs field. The gates and their IDs should follow a non-recursive topological order. No gate could exist in two sections at the same time.

7.2 VDCS Library

The VDCS library is the core of all prototypes. It includes the implementations for the communication functions, garbling, evaluation, and re-randomization

functions, different encryption/decryption schemes implementations, and other useful utility functions. The garbling implementation is not optimized to the different optimizations mentioned in the background section. The VDCS Library is common between all system nodes.

7.3 Client Nodes

Client nodes contain the preprocessor that scans the originally written code and converts it into the newly generated code that contains the VDCS Library calls. The reason behind the use of the preprocessor is to showcase the advantage of having a part of the cycle execution parallelizable, and this is done by generating multiple threads at the beginning of the code to request computations. So, the first part of the cycle would be done in parallel while the evaluations will be done sequentially as the order of the code dictates. This also allows for hybrid execution so that the client would only outsource the parts of the code that it desires, and the rest of the code would be executed on the client's machine.

7.4 Server Nodes

Server Nodes utilize heavily the functions of the VDCS library as well as extra functions that handle keeping track of the different requests and operating on each separately. Servers are multi-threaded. A server node could garble, re-randomize, evaluate, and communicate with other nodes in the system.

7.5 Decentralized Directory of Service

We use the EOS blockchain to achieve decentralization in our system. The Directory of Service is deployed as a contract on the blockchain. We are using EOS because it uses a secure Proof-of-Stake algorithm. All directory of service interactions are done on the blockchain, while servers' or clients' interactions are done off-chain. The contract and the blockchain are used to keep track of all registered users, their balances, and the transfer of payment among them. The directory of service has two main actions: register and fetch cycle. The register takes the required data from the user wishing to register on the directory service. The required data to register must include their user name, IP, port, public key, type (client or server), and processing power. This data is then registered to the database in the directory of service for later usage. As for the fetch cycle action, it takes the number of servers required to complete the computation and their processing power. Then, it searches the database to find the servers that meet the requirement of the fetch cycle action and send their communication data to the user to use it to construct the cycle and communicate with the servers to start the computation.

7.6 Experiments and Results

We tested on client code containing more than up to 100 different parallel outsourcing requests with varying circuit sizes. The minimum number of gates tested was 14 and the maximum number of gates was 32,000 per request. We tested having more than one server, up to 6 servers, as a security parameter. The current prototype is not efficient and is inherently slower than normal code execution. Therefore, optimizations, discussed in previous sections, need to be made in the garbling scheme as well as the network overhead. Furthermore, we were targeting security, verifiability, privacy and decentralization. Security and privacy are guaranteed in our construction as explained. Thus, it achieved its goals of verifiability, security, privacy, and decentralization.

8 Conclusion and Future Works

In this work, We introduced and utilized a variant of the Ananth et al. [3] proposed construction to design and prototype a verifiable decentralized computing resources sharing system.

As mentioned in a previous section, we do allow the support for fault-tolerance, although we do not implement or consider it in our prototype. Therefore, it should be further investigated what scheme should be applied to allow for efficient fault tolerance.

Furthermore, to achieve decentralization and a communication channel between all nodes. We proposed that the whole system become on a block chain, where network nodes are the servers, the clients, the miners, and the validators as well. Any node can act as one or all of those. This construction should facilitate the payment after the cycle is complete and guarantee the anonymity and privacy of the clients as well as the servers, as explained earlier. However, we did not investigate this proposal thoroughly and left it open for future work.

We do not propose an optimized scheduling algorithm to select the perfect set of servers for each client. However, we leave such an investigation for future work as we consider outside of this paper's scope.

Another problem is the modular roots which are needed for re-randomization. As explained previously, we managed to find a solution that works without compromising security; however, it would be a huge addition if that problem is researched thoroughly for an efficient and secure solution.

Another interesting question is whether it would be possible to use the El-Gamal over the field of elliptic curves rather than \mathbb{Z}_p^* . This would let us evade the complexity with using \mathbb{Z}_p^* .

Alternative topologies/architectures are also an interesting direction for future work. In specific, a possible question is whether it would be possible to have a setting where the client sends a single message to n servers who do not communicate together and return partial results that can be combined for the full result. This essentially represents a star graph and would be very attractive due to the obliquity of the servers of one another, and hence, collusion-based attacks would be difficult to achieve.

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